

BIO-SUSHY

Sustainable surface protection by glass-like hybrid and biomaterials coatings

Deliverable D3.1

Knowledge and data exchange infrastructure specifications

Deliverable Information

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¹ PU = PUBLIC fully open ((warning) automatically posted online on the Project Results platforms)

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Publishable Summary

This report describes the data collection, curation, management and sharing infrastructure of the BIO-SUSHY project. The system is supporting storage and FAIRification of all research outputs (sampling plans, study designs, *in vitro* and *in silico* method specifications, protocols, SOPs, and the data created, as well as guidelines, reports, training materials and publications), *i.e.* making them Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable, for internal knowledge exchange between BIO-SUSHY WP2, WP3 and WP4 partners and finally for long-term storage and public sharing. It is assisting the planning of the preparation of the coatings and the experimental and computational safety and sustainability assessment for the use cases and the organisation of the complex sample and information flow between partners and work packages required during their execution. This is achieved by the combination of four data management tools, the BIO-SUSHY Registry, the instance map tool, the BIO-SUSHY Google Shared Drive and the data collector, together providing the infrastructure for the customised BIO-SUSHY data lake. While the first three are focusing on the F (Findable) and A (Accessible) in the form of a one-stop shop for all information as well as a visual representation of the links between different research outputs, the fourth is fostering the I (Interoperable) and R (Re-usable) by providing automated workflows to translate the (meta)data as provided by the partners into computer-actionable files following the harmonised BIO-SUSHY data schema designed to fulfil requirements from data producers of WP2 (starting material characterisation and production processes), WP3 (functional and toxicity predictions) and WP4 (hazard and exposure estimation) as well as data users from WP4 (safety and life cycle assessment).

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Table of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable
FAIR4RS	FAIR for Research Software
PFAS	Per- and Polyfluoroalkyl Substances
SSbD	Safe and Sustainable by Design
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
FIP	FAIR Implementation Profiles
PARC	Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals
WPx	Work Package x
KMT	Knowledge Management Translators
ELN	Electronic Lab Notebook
LIMS	Laboratory Information Management System
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure

1. Objectives

As a part of its open science philosophy, BIO-SUSHY is implementing high quality knowledge and data management first for internal use and then public sharing. It is using state-of-the-art data sharing concepts, approaches and tools jointly developed together with the [MACRAMÉ project](#). It is improving research output/data documentation towards full implementation of the FAIR¹ (findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable) and FAIR for Research Software² (FAIR4RS) principles aligned with and extending community standards. This report describes the initial version of this data management system consisting of the BIO-SUSHY Registry as the central information access point, a visualisation tool (instance map) for the planning of information flows, and automated workflows for data harmonisation and enrichment (data collector). These implement the concept of on-the-fly FAIRification enhancing the data management quality at the partner institutions keeping the established experimental workflows intact for easy adoption. New data requirements identified while progressing the use cases is continuously addressed. (Meta)data completeness is improved by enriching the partner-specific (meta)data reporting formats and re-integrating the updated files as new versions of the data in the Registry.

2. Data generation in BIO-SUSHY

The development of new coatings replacing PFAS components is based and guided by the SSbD methodology considering the entire life cycle and value chain of the new products. To this purpose, 3 use cases have been designed to provide competitive coating solutions with lower toxicities and environmental footprints as PFAS alternatives. Successful execution of the cases requires interdisciplinary research interlinking computational modelling, SSbD methodology and material development, in an iterative carousel approach, with key nodes of innovation.

Durable water- and oil-repellent properties of the use case coatings are being achieved by:

1. Bio-based thermoplastic powder coating formulations for food tray application: BIO-SUSHY coatings will be applied onto cellulosic fibre mat, by spray or powder deposition, which will further undergo a curing process (melting of thermoplastic powder or curing of hybrid sol-gel coating). Dry powder application onto cellulosic food trays is done by electrostatic powder spraying or alternative electric field powder application processes. Melting and film formation is carried out by infrared or hot calendering. After cooling, the mat is thermoformed (between 120°C and 180°C for 1 second) to a 3D shape (e.g. food tray) using an innovative “dry moulded fibre method,” instead of using the standard “wet pulp” production method where water acts as the main carrier for fibres to the mould.
2. Hybrid water-based coatings, based on sol-gel with high content of organics to provide highly flexible layers compatible with textile applications: The precursor-synthesised sol-gels, along with functional chemicals, will be deposited onto textile fabrics in one step by padding. This is a dipping procedure where excess formulation is squeezed out by the rollers from the textile fabrics and then cured in an oven or by UV processes. This method allows the liquid formulation to penetrate between the fibre in the fabric. The main governing factors in the pad-coating process are (a) the nature of the textile substrate, (b) substrate speed, (c) surface

tension and viscosity of the formulation, (d) dry content and (e) nip pressure and the speed of the roll coater.

3. Hybrid coatings on glass containers for cosmetic applications based on sol-gel with high content in inorganic part to provide improved scratch, thermal and chemical resistance: Inner application of cosmetic glass containers allows to unsure quality, and complete availability of the products and content are protected and made to last longer. Hybrid coatings will be applied by inner spray using long nozzle and small spray head followed by post-curing. Using glass-like sol-gel technology for coating, with an emphasis on mechanical durability and low adhesion of fluids, will help the aspects of reuse as End-of-life scenario.

The aim of the project is, besides the development of high-performance coatings described so far, to integrate safety and sustainability considerations following the SSbD framework into every stage of the material development stage to minimise toxicity and environmental impact of the new products. The BIO-SUSHY SSbD approach is, thus, composed of the following tasks:

- Production of sol-gel precursors including hydrophobic additives and functional linkers, partly biobased, to serve as starting materials for the coatings or for surface functionalisation (SIKEMIA)
- Optimisation of the formulations and corresponding thermoplastic powder coating (WoodK+) and hybrid coatings from sol-gel technologies (MANO, RESCOLL and IFTH).
- Physicochemical performance testing (WoodK+, MANO, RESCOLL, IFTH)
- Computational optimisation of functionality (CNR, PQSAR)
- Occupational exposure evaluation (ITENE)
- Human and environmental toxicology testing (UNIVLEEDS, ITENE, RESCOLL, MANO)
- Computational data gap filling for physico-chemical characterisation, human and environmental risk assessment (PQSAR, CNR)
- Environmental and social life-cycle assessment (MANO, WOODK+, IFTH, RESCOLL)
- Up-scaling and validation (MANO, WOODK+, RESCOLL and IFTH)
- Performance/SSbD and social acceptance evaluation (ECOZEMA, ZSI)
- Stakeholder consultation in the context of the value chain analysis (ZSI).

These tasks are not executed sequentially but, at the same time, implement important feedback loops, achieving the transition from safety and sustainability assessment of final products to guaranteeing safety and sustainability of the final product by integrating these criteria into the design process.

It is clear that the list above is not describing the complete BIO-SUSHY project, and this was also not the goal. Instead, it is meant to show the many players involved in data production with many dependencies on data provided by other partners used as input for downstream data generation, analysis and decision making. For example, physicochemical data on the starting material either collected by the coating developers or predicted by data-driven or physics-based modelling approaches are needed for selection of the human and ecotox test battery, occupational exposure estimation as well as environmental and social life cycle assessment (LCA). All this information will

then be integrated into the SSbD evaluation of the products, which then guides new optimisation cycles of the formulations, production techniques, and scale up. This need for intensive and timely knowledge exchange between partners but especially also between WPs was envisioned at proposal stage, visualised by showing WP2, WP3 and WP4 as a highly interlinked, inseparable group in the WP overview (see Figure 1), and acknowledged by bringing in a partner (7P9) specifically for coordinating data harmonisation and sharing and providing new tools for planning of the complex material and data flows, knowledge exchange, and centralised data tracking, management and storage.

Figure 1: Illustrated PERT-chart of the BIO-SUSHY Project structure, individual work packages (WPs) and the workflow and dependencies between them.

3. Knowledge collection and transfer within and between work packages

As described in the previous chapter, many partners are generating or (re-)using data and information of many different types. These are coming from documentation of formulation and coating processes including important production parameters, chemical data sheets and supply chain information of starting materials (for safety assessment and LCA), information on production sites (for occupational exposure assessments), safety dossiers including data from similar chemicals and materials, life-cycle inventories and then, the computational and safety testing methods developed by and applied in BIO-SUSHY. To be re-usable by other project partners, the shared information needs to include more than the data (numbers) per se but needs to be accompanied by study designs translating needs into actions, method specifications describing the measurement principles, protocols and standard operating procedures (SOP), and clear provenance trails to the origin of the data. Data to be shared includes not only data generated for the final coating of the three use cases but every produced data point with their specific protocols from early development, calibration, and control measurements to document integration of all aspects (functionality, economical validity, safety, sustainability) in the development cycles according to the SSbD Framework.

To enable such a very intense multi-way exchange of information and knowledge, a customised data infrastructure is needed, which puts WP3 with its task to coordinate data harmonisation, central data storage and support of the partners in preparing data for re-use in the centre of the project. At the moment, there is no out-of-the-box data system available providing the functionality and flexibility

needed by the BIO-SUSHY project. It is also not expected that such a system will become available in the near future due to the fast speed requirements on hybrid and biomaterials coatings and the rapid development in the regulatory framework related to SSbD. Building a new database specifically for BIO-SUSHY was also not an option due to time constraints and the fact that this system would be outdated very quickly, potentially even during the runtime of BIO-SUSHY, because of the just mentioned changing requirements. Therefore, BIO-SUSHY adopted an alternative approach building around the concepts of a data lake and data packages building this lake, in which all information about an experimental or computational study are stored, first, in the formats of the data providers and then in an additional structured and harmonised and finally semantically annotated way. This is depicted in Figure 2 specifically focusing on WP3 with its data-driven and physics-based data gap filling tasks. With the help of application programming interfaces (APIs), data storage, harmonisation (at least partly) and translation of the data into different formats can be performed (semi-)automatically. The data can then be provided as requested by the data users, by analysis and visualisation user interfaces and by public databases for long-term storage. More functionalities will be added throughout the project.

Figure 2: Data management concept in which all data from experiment, computational approaches and public resources is integrated to build the data lake used as input for data-driven modelling to guide the SSbD decisions for the development of the new coatings as well as to prepare uploading to public databases.

A data lake is a centralized repository that allows users to store all structured and unstructured data at any scale. Data is stored as-is, without having to first be structured according to a specific data model as is the case in relational databases and commonly used data warehouses. This architecture was selected to be highly flexible with respect to stored data types and formats provided by the individual partners and to not postpone data exchange by first having to define the relational data

model and transform all data into this structure. Even at the current state, it would still be impossible to fully define the final data model. Data needs are still being defined in an interactive exchange between data providers and data users. Detailed material structure specifications usable in modelling application, physicochemical characterisation and toxicity, exposure and environmental and social sustainability evaluation has all to be combined to guide the development of the new SSbD coatings. If new data is requested in this process, it can easily be made available by updating the files in the data lake while it would require an update of the data model implemented in a relational database and potentially even the re-upload of all data if larger changes had to be introduced to the model.

However, the flexibility of a data lake also comes with a cost. Data needs to be documented on two different levels to be findable and extractable from the data lake (high level) and transformable and restructurable to be (re-)usable in the many data use cases of BIO-SUSHY (input generation for modelling and simulations, occupational exposure, selection and execution of safety testing methods, and life-cycle assessment, life-cycle costing and social life-cycle assessment). This is achieved by providing standardised metadata, a description of the data schema implemented in each dataset and a mapping of these data schemas to a harmonised BIO-SUSHY data schema building the foundation for interoperability. Data management guidelines and support including relevant tools provided by 7P9 to the consortium to prepare the data for integration into the data lake are described in the following sections.

4. Data lifecycle and (meta)data shepherding

As a consequence of pressure from the scientific community for improving reproducibility but especially also from funding agencies requesting optimal exploitation of data generated with public funding by providing and re-using public data, the FAIR data principles¹ (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable) were introduced and recently extended to also cover research software² (FAIR for Research Software, FAIR4RS). Many European and global initiatives and projects are working on practical implementations of these principles. Data management plans based on FAIR are now deliverables of every project funded by the EU and additional tools like [FAIR implementation profiles \(FIPs\) developed by the GO FAIR initiative](#) are endorsed by many projects like [WorldFAIR](#) and the [Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals \(PARC\)](#).

This shows that FAIRification of data, i.e. making data findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable, is generally accepted as essential for being able to fully exploit the knowledge contained in the immense mass of produced data. However, FAIRification is often still seen as something needed only when the data is shared for reuse, leading to two issues that extremely reduce the amount of available FAIR data:

- 1) FAIRification is an external process outside of the normal handling of data in the research laboratories, often depicted as the sixth stage of the data management life cycle. This leads to extra work added to the already heavy workload of the researchers, which is postponed as long as possible or even completely avoided.

- 2) Since data is often only available in customised formats, first analysis of the data and internal data integration is performed in a manual, often time-consuming and project specific way. This is the case even if FAIRification could lead to increased automation and, thus, time reduction e.g. for making all required information accessible to allow the direct use by other partners and WPs and for formatting data to be usable in existing standard tools and workflows for further processing (e.g. use in modelling, exposure evaluation and life-cycle assessment). Project-internal data users used to such unFAIR working habits are not pushing for and are hesitant to support later FAIRification since it comes too late to give them direct benefits.

In contrast, harmonisation and sharing of (meta)data in BIO-SUSHY is being integrated as part of the normal experimental and computational workflow to profit from FAIRness within the project and provide all outcomes in a FAIR way at the end. Figure 3 (adapted from Papadiamantis et al.³) shows how such an early integration maps onto the data management life cycle (not to be confused with the material life cycle), where FAIRification is started at the production stages and then completed, while the data moves through the life-cycle stages. Clear documentation of the experimental design in the life-cycle phase 1 “Plan & Design” increases the FAIRness of the data and specifically supports the re-use part of the FAIR concept, since this information gives the data customer (i.e. the first user, as well as a re-user in the form of other partners) important details to understand the data and its reliability. Collection of the data and its analysis in phases 2 and 3 (Collection & Create and Process & Analyse) are subsequently utilising harmonised and interoperable data reporting formats and workflows directly or are semi-automatically translated into these. This guides the definition and collection of the needed metadata. The remaining steps then add more technical information like unique, persistent identifiers (e.g. DOIs), licences and other biographical metadata for improved findability and accessibility. In this way, the data is FAIR (according to the FAIR criteria used in each step) after step 5 without the need to have a 6th FAIRification step separating the FAIR sharing from storage, as proposed e.g. in Papadiamantis et al.³

Figure 3: Five phases of the data management life cycle. In contrast to other depictions where FAIRification is a sixth phase, FAIRification in BIO-SUSHY is starting in the Plan & Design phase and then continues throughout all other phases continuously enhancing the FAIRness of the data (on-the-fly FAIR).

This continuous, on-the-fly FAIRification along the data management life cycle stages brings with it the need for clear definitions of task for the different roles involved³: 'data creators', 'analysts', 'curators', 'managers', 'customers' and 'shepherds'. All these roles are present in BIO-SUSHY with the data creators and curators distributed across WP2, WP3 and WP4, data analysts and customers represented by WP4 and WP5, and data managers and shepherds in WP3. Since the concept of data shepherds is quite new and still relatively unknown, it will be described here in more detail with the specific tasks performed during the first period of the BIO-SUSHY project.

First, we must clearly state what the data shepherd is not: the authority in the project that defines what data to collect and demands specific harmonisation / standardisation approaches, file formats and reporting standards. Instead, all BIO-SUSHY WP2, WP3 and WP4 partners are working together, as part of the experimental design and data requirement analysis of all project parts, on the definition of data completeness and quality checklists, reporting standards and corresponding SOP/protocol and (meta)data reporting formats. However, for alignment and increasing interoperability both within the project, and with the relevant community activities and the forming European digital materials ecosystem, advanced understanding and knowledge on the global data management and FAIRification landscape and the available FAIR Enabling and Supporting Resources is required. This need for integration experts and support personnel resulted in the definition and establishment of data stewards⁴ and recently of data shepherds³ and the related Knowledge Management Translators (KMTs)^{5,6}. The latter two can be described as an enhanced version of the first, who not only oversees the data management, handling and quality control processes, but can communicate in a clear and simple language with all roles (see above) and resolve any misunderstandings. Data shepherds, specifically, lead the data quality control and FAIRness efforts, selection and/or development of the appropriate data management toolset according to both the data types and the requirements of specific partners, as well as the continuous optimisation of data workflows, including technical developments to facilitate data curation, annotation, and cleansing.

To provide these services to all partners, a continuous, centralised (meta)data shepherding process was established in BIO-SUSHY. This started with multiple trainings and workshops on data literacy, i.e. familiarity with current FAIR and quality data management / sharing approaches and tools. This was then continued with specific workshops and trainings on the proposed and now implemented data management tools, which are described in detail in the following sections. Together with the use case teams as well as individual partners, these tools were then applied to collect information on starting materials, document and visualise the processes of formulation and coating production, communicate data requirements between data users and data producers, and transfer the first examples of BIO-SUSHY data from partner-internal formats to a harmonised BIO-SUSHY (meta)data format. Both the original, partner-specific and harmonised files are being combined into data packages and used to populate the data lake as described above. This guarantees that no information is lost, and, at the same time, information is available in a human- and machine-actionable way either directly used in this form for long-term storage and public sharing or to be automatically transferred into standardised file formats if these become available for advanced materials like coatings.

The data shepherd will continue to support all partners by monitoring data management practises at individual partners and proposing options and tools for the harmonisation of data, improving completeness, interoperability and FAIRness. One important aspect is the further automation of the transformation of partner-specific formats into the harmonised BIO-SUSHY format. Frequent re-

evaluation of the completeness of the provided information for the use cases output will be performed, and improved reporting guidelines resulting from these activities (e.g. implementing the concept of method-specific reporting) will be proposed to the scientific community and standardisation bodies (ISO, CEN).

5. Indexing the data lake: the BIO-SUSHY Registry

Many pieces of information and knowledge are generated and collected as research outputs of the use cases during formulation selection, chemical modification, production of coatings, safety and sustainability evaluation and upscaling and need to be stored in the data lake. All this information (materials, sampling plans, study designs, method specifications, protocols, SOPs, computational models, software, workflows, and the data created by them, as well as guidelines, reports, and publications), here also referred to as (meta)data, is coming from multiple partners and needs to be shared with the consortium in a timely manner and in parts be collaboratively edited. As already mentioned above, to avoid delays caused by waiting times resulting from the need to agree on file formats and data models between all partners, adoption of these by all partners, or the transfer of data into these formats, the first data management and FAIRification actions of the BIO-SUSHY project concentrated on providing findability and accessibility (the first two letters of FAIR). This was achieved by the combination of a data storage system, the data lake, with a central BIO-SUSHY Registry (see Figure 4), which indexes high-level metadata, like name, type of resource, short description, provider, and documentation completion status, as well as the link to where the resource is available (see **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.** and Figure 6). The material examples in the figures show the flexibility of the system, which can handle all types of materials from standard starting chemicals (Figure 5) to mixtures as starting points for the sol-gel process (Figure 6) to final coatings on specific substrates (not shown). Specific details, which can vary from one type of material to the next are given in the linked resource files, which are described in more detail in Section 7 (including their harmonisation approach). Thus, the Registry provides high-level metadata like type and provenance, while the linked files collect the low-level scientific and technical metadata, i.e. scientific and technical information for quality control and reproducibility, and the data.

Statuses of resources are ranging from “planned”, over different levels of completeness (i.e. “under development”, “internal review”, and “external review”) to “publicly shared”. In this way, the Registry can already document the need to generate a specific resource identified during the design stage of the use cases and the responsible partner. By changing the status, all partners can then be informed about the progress of data generation, collection and documentation for this resource (e.g. ordering and arrival of starting material, development of a SOP, or collection of data, and location and access routes to the current, most up-to-date version are clearly defined).

The screenshot shows the 'Resources' page of the BIO-SUSHY Registry. At the top, there are navigation tabs for 'Study designs', 'Resources' (which is active), 'Use cases', 'Organisations', 'People', and 'API'. A 'Register a new resource' button is located in the top right corner. Below the navigation is a 'Filter resources' section with three dropdown menus for 'Resource type', 'Use case', and 'Status'. The main content is a table listing four resources.

ID	Name	Type	Status
zmd9jh5s34ts	1TEST_RESCOLL_2302589-0010-ME01_Application	Protocol or SOP	Version for internal review
3cd4jketxnr3	1TEST_RESCOLL_2302589-0010-ME01_Coated_textile	Material	Version for internal review
3slrkkhahsn	1TEST_RESCOLL_2302589-0010-ME01_Curing	Protocol or SOP	Version for internal review
jsyc9qqfswdu	1TEST_RESCOLL_2302589-0010-ME01_Diodo_contact_angle	Data	Version for internal review

Figure 4: Screenshot of the BIO-SUSHY Registry showing four resources (1 material, 2 protocols and one data file).

The screenshot shows the high-level description of a material resource. The title is 'acid'. The details are as follows:

- ID:** asb6vw4dv4s3
- Type of resource:** Material
- Status:** Published in peer-reviewed journal / validated
- Resource link/file:** <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/...>
- Description:** A table with columns 'name', 'CAS', and 'InChIKey'. The 'name' column contains a blurred entry.
- Use cases:** Textile
- Contributors:** [blurred] Owner / Main contact
- License:** /

Figure 5: Screenshot of the high-level description of a BIO-SUSHY material resource for a starting material.

2102238-0086_Mixture Update this resource

ID: 3uj59du6sr36

Type of resource: Material

Status: Version for internal review

Resource link/file: <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/...>

Description: RESCOLL Formulation No.: 2102238-0086
Study Design Node Id: ea9f9916-42f0-4258-b177-7ca501c94780

Reg Id	Substance name	Mass percentage (intended)	Mass (intended)	Mass
nan	Water	93.3680	186.7360	186.96
https://registry.bio-...	acid	1.6400	3.2800	3.28

Figure 6: Screenshot of the high-level description of a BIO-SUSHY material resource for a RESCOLL formulation.

Formats, in which the actual resources are prepared, vary from one partner to another. For example, method descriptions and protocols/SOPs are often available as text documents (Microsoft Word, Google docs or pdf) while data is provided as spreadsheets (Microsoft Excel). However, some partners also use electronic lab notebooks (ELN) and automatic data capturing workflows or proprietary file formats. As explained above, at this early stage of the project, it is most important to not cause time delays by not sharing (meta)data between partners and work packages. Therefore, instead of forcing all resources into a predefined template, the Registry supports all these different reporting styles. Use cases can start discussing results on this basis with missing technical interoperability replaced by human interactions and discussions. To provide the needed flexibility, a resource is just specified by an URL, which in many cases links to a folder in the BIO-SUSHY Google Shared Drive but could also redirect to e.g. a page of an ELN. Using the paid Google service instead of the free version provides higher data security and access restrictions including enforcing the hosting of the data on European servers.

BIO-SUSHY WP2, WP3 and WP4 partners have started populating the Registry with information specifically on starting materials, formulations, safety information extracted from chemical data sheets as well as on previous / preliminary experiments. In this way, the status of data management at each partner, used management tools, file formats and data completeness are documented in these examples. This is now being used to identify commonalities in data documentation, to define minimal data and metadata to be reported for each type of research output and find (meta)data gaps hindering the reuse of the data internally and later public sharing. Based on this analysis, recommendations for improvements of data management at each partner to fill the identified gaps are being suggested, harmonised (meta)data schemas and data transfer formats are proposed and aligned to community standards, still allowing flexibility to adapt to specific data types. Mappings between the data schemas used internally by a partner to these harmonised transfer formats and semi-automatic data transformation procedure are being created and are described in Section 7. This improvement of the data management practices will continue throughout the project and will finally generate data of highest FAIRness levels for public sharing. Even if this represents a major shift

in the way data of large project consortia is managed, high quality and computer actionability will be achieved with little changes in the partner-internal workflows with respect to used data management tools and formats and with manual data transformation limited to the absolute minimum.

6. Structuring the data lake: instance maps to design and document complex studies

Besides high-level data documentation and easy access *via* the BIO-SUSHY Registry, the complex design of the use cases and the related experimental workflows puts additional demands on the knowledge transfer with respect to showing the links between resources and the (virtual) flow of data but also physical transfer of materials and samples between work packages and partners. Instance maps have been successfully applied for such purposes and are now interfaced with the BIO-SUSHY Registry to not only visualise the workflows but also give direct access to the data.

Instance maps were first used as organisational structure in the data curation efforts for the [NIKC \(NanoInformatics Knowledge Commons\)](#); they enable users to follow nanomaterial transformations, while capturing necessary metadata. An instance is defined as the nanomaterial in a medium at a specific moment in time. An instance map then represents a flow chart of the nanomaterial fate represented as a directed, often tree-like graph built out of nodes connected by edges represented as arrows to show the directionality. To support the quick generation of such maps, a specific software tool was developed in the [NanoCommons project](#) and integrated into the data management infrastructure⁷. The tool introduced a couple of modifications and new features:

1. Besides the five node categories (instance, material, medium, property, and supplementary) of the original approach, transformation protocol nodes explicitly describing the processes leading from one instance to the next, protocols/SOP nodes for experimental details and data nodes were added.
2. Information resources can be associated with each node.

These new features make instance maps an optimal planning and monitoring tool for the experimental work by visualising the BIO-SUSHY use cases or parts of them like mixing the starting materials (Figure 7) or information integrated in the SSbD assessment (Figure 8) by showing material flows and dependencies of experiments.

Nodes can be linked to the resources in the Registry providing structure to the many resources e.g. associated with a use case, giving easy access to all information needed to start the next phase of the study, and in this way, supporting the management of the studies and of the overall project. Planning of the experimental work and workflows using the tool has been started as a series of co-creative training sessions resulting in partial instance maps as show in the examples, which are now further refined and filled with / linked to the generated Registry resources.

Figure 7: Screenshot of an instance map representing the mixing procedure of the starting materials as the first step of creating coatings for the hybrid coatings on glass containers for cosmetic applications use case.

Figure 8: Screenshot of an instance map representing the early planning stage of the safety and sustainability evaluation of coatings.

7. Filling the data lake: (meta)data harmonisation and enrichment

As described in Section 4, FAIR data sharing requires harmonisation of data to achieve interoperability, but current lab workflows are not developed around standardised data exchange formats. Instead, they use customised files or ELNs / laboratory information management systems (LIMS) with customised data models. BIO-SUSHY is not different with e.g. RESCOLL using an internal LIMS while other partners use Excel-based data analysis and storage. Completely changing the data storage formats within partner organisations to be based on a common standard is not feasible and, even more important, not sensible since it would require retraining personnel just for this project and would remove the flexibility from the lab workflows to report all important parameters, without making the data model unmanageably complex. Data reporting templates were proposed for (nano)materials in the past⁷, which expected some standard metadata to be filled in together with the data. However, one could argue that harmonisation and interoperability require in principle only that the (meta)data is reported in a digital form but not which specific structure is used. The FAIR principle accordingly only requires that the data is reported according to domain-agreed community standards. As these standards are well documented, translating from one to another is possible similarly to translating languages. BIO-SUSHY is taking the idea even further and accepts customised partner-specific files. To achieve harmonisation and interoperability, these files have in most cases still to be improved to 1) guarantee that all required metadata is available to make the data understandable for others (either as part of the modified (meta)data file or as accompanying metadata files) and 2) the data structure in the (meta)data file is documented to allow mapping of data between different metadata schemas (the original partner-specific schema and a harmonised BIO-SUSHY schema).

7.1. (Meta)data completeness

(Meta)data completeness in BIO-SUSHY is, on one hand, defined by the data requirements of the project-internal data users. However, for final public sharing of the data without additional manual effort, i.e. on-the-fly FAIRification, cross-discipline and community specific (meta)data requirements (minimal reporting checklists and standards) have also to be considered from the start. The latter is achieved by consulting metadata standards endorsed by the FAIR community and relevant scientific communities and selection of the most appropriate ones guided by the data shepherd. For example, bibliographic and data provenance metadata requirements can be taken from different web standards and data services (e.g. [DataCite](https://datacite.org), schema.org and bioschemas.org, [DDI](https://ddi.org)). Again, it is important that the BIO-SUSHY solution provides the information requested by the (minimal) information standards, but it does not necessarily need to follow the exact same format or even data structure. In this way, multiple standards can be combined, e.g. if they are missing some but not the same metadata fields considered essential by BIO-SUSHY. Additionally, standards can also be reused only partly if only substructures of the complete data schema are relevant (e.g. the fields related to authors, origin and supporting citation of the DataCite schema but not necessarily funding).

Completeness with respect to all the data usages in BIO-SUSHY is currently established by collecting the data requirements from WP3 with respect to input generation for modelling and simulations and WP4 with respect to toxicity testing, occupational exposure estimation and (social) LCA and mapping them onto data provision from WP2 and WP3. Since much of the metadata is needed for multiple

applications and can come from multiple sources (experimental vs. computational, specific partners for the different use cases), data exchange needs are first discussed in the use cases or even between individual pairs or groups of partners. However, the results of this metadata scoping exercise are then combined into one central and global data model so that data users can check if a specific (meta)data field is already planned to be collected, by whom and using which method and data producers do not have to send the same data multiple times to different data users and potentially in different formats. A part of an early version of this harmonised BIO-SUSHY data schema is shown in Figure 9, using the visualisation capacity of the instance map tool to demonstrate the structure between different (meta)data points. In addition, a JSON file showing exactly the same structure is maintained, which builds the basis for the computer-actionable documentation of the BIO-SUSHY data model. JSON has the advantage that the structure can easily be amended and locally re-structured to integrate new requirements that show up during further progression of the use cases. Additionally, the data model documentation can be further enriched by including information on the expected data type, relationships between data entries, and even annotation with ontology terms essential for integrating BIO-SUSHY data into the semantic framework of the materials data ecosystem. Combined with the data collector described in the next subsection, which is used for extracting data from partner-specific files, this setup provided the flexibility to generate the first versions of the datasets now and can be used to update these automatically, when improvements in data completeness and/or data documentation/annotation are requested by the data providers or users.

Figure 9: Part of the harmonised BIO-SUSHY (meta)data schema used to describe starting materials.

7.2. Data collector

To reduce the time invested into data management and harmonisation by the data providers, the data collector software library is being developed by 7P9. This library is used to extract data from partner-specific data files, translate the data according to the harmonised BIO-SUSHY data schema, and enrich the data by querying public services. The process is described below with the example of a coating formulation from partner RESCOLL. Starting point is the data file, which is generated by the LIMS used by RESCOLL, that holds information on the starting materials, mixing information and basic characterisation of the coating (see Figure 10).

2302589-0010-ME01		Matières Premières	Ordre d'ajout	Pourcentage théorique	Masse théorique	Masse pesée
	eau		1	90.3680	180.7360	180.8100
	acid		1	1.6400	3.2800	3.3000
			1	0.1120	0.2240	0.2800
			2	0.1960	0.3920	0.4000
			2	2.5600	5.1200	5.1200
			3	0.1400	0.2800	0.2900
			3	3.0000	6.0000	6.0400
			3	0.5000	1.0000	1.0200
			4	0.0840	0.1680	0.1700
			4	0.7000	1.4000	1.4200
			4	0.7000	1.4000	1.4100

Figure 10: Data sheet for a RESCOLL coating formulation with information on the starting materials and concentrations.

After the data producer has uploaded a data file to the BIO-SUSHY Google Shared Drive, the semi-automated workflow visualised in Figure 11 is started. Since the content of Excel worksheets cannot be directly accessed on the drive, the files are downloaded and stored locally for data extraction. A customised script based on the data collector is used to fill the harmonised BIO-SUSHY data schema for coatings with all information available in the file by accessing individual cells or blocks of cells in the spreadsheets. At the same time, the script performs basic checks on the content, like expected data type, to guarantee the consistency of the integrated data. In principle, the data collector could also directly access RESCOLL's LIMS without the need for EXCEL files for data exchange. However, this would need establishing a secure exchange between the two systems and exchange policies, which is out of scope of the BIO-SUSHY project.

Additional information, needed for complete documentation and (meta)data completeness not provided in the RESCOLL data files, can be provided in additional files of different formats. This is shown in Figure 11 as the second input in the form of the RESCOLL material information sheet, which provides CAS registry numbers as well as supplier and batch information for the starting materials. For each starting material, a parallel workflow is started. This extracts, if not already available from previous executions of the workflow, additional chemical identifiers (InChI, InChI key, SMILES) and basic physicochemical properties from web services like the [Chemical Abstract Services Common Chemistry](#) and [PubChem](#). This information is then stored according to the (meta)data schema for starting materials as individual material entries in the BIO-SUSHY Registry. Unique identifiers assigned by the Registry and a subset of the starting material information are then stored as part of the coating data. In this way, the starting materials are chemically defined in the coating data and additional data is accessible by following the link to the starting material Registry entries. Finally, information on the mixture (mixing order, concentrations, masses) and basic characteristics are added and new material entities for the mixture and coating are created on the Registry. The Registry entities are linked to the Google Drive that stores the (meta)data files in both the original RESCOLL format and the harmonised format.

Figure 11: Workflow to extract information on the starting materials from data files on coating formulations provided by RESCOLL as well as public webservices.

```

system:
  PID: {...}
  name:
    value: "2302589-0010"
  numberSubsystems: {...}
  subsystem:
    PID:
      value: 2
    chemicalComponent:
      0:
        chemicalName:
          internalName:
            provenance: {...}
            value: "eau [redacted]"
          preferredName:
            value: "[redacted] water"
        parameters:
          processParameters:
            mass:
              intended: {...}
              unit: "g"
              value: "180.8100"
            massConcentration: {...}
            mixingOrder: {...}
          property: {}
      1:
        chemicalName:
          internalName:
            provenance: {...}
            value: "[redacted] acid"
          preferredName:
            value: "[redacted] acid"

```

Figure 12: RESCOLL coating data in JSON format structured according to the harmonised BIO-SUSHY (meta)data schema.

Parts of the resulting harmonised coating (meta)data file are shown in Figure 12. It has to be noted here that the file format was chosen for computer actionability not human readability. Due to its well-defined structure, data can be either directly used as input for the different modelling approaches or further transformed to fit the need of data users (computational, safety and exposure assessment, LCA) with respect to content and format. Following the study plan documented and visualised in the instance maps (see Figure 8) the information on the coatings is then further enriched by advanced characterisation. This includes data from the production of the coating (e.g. information on the substrates, production parameters) and up-scaling from WP2, from modelling in WP3 and risk and sustainability assessment from WP4 with all related protocols, SOPs and documentation of results and conclusion. These are stored as updated versions of the coating Registry entries linked to additional methods, protocols, SOPs, and data Registry entries. This data enrichment with information coming from different partners and the workflow to integrate the data into the Registry are visualised in Figure 13.

Figure 13: Workflow to enrich RESCOLL coating data with process information, physicochemical characterisation and hazard predictions using QSAR models provided by PQSAR.

As mentioned above, the harmonised, highly structured (meta)data files can then be further transformed to provide for the data needs of downstream tasks. Figure 14 shows a simple example of such further analysis performed automatically using the harmonised coating (meta)data. Concentrations of the starting materials in two different RESCOLL coatings are extracted from the Registry and then visualised. The differences can then be correlated with the functional and SSbD properties for further optimisation of the coatings.

Figure 14: Comparison of the concentrations of starting materials in two RESCOLL coatings using automated data extraction from the harmonised (meta)data files.

As a conclusion of this section, we want to highlight a critical feature of the automatic procedure that profits from features of the Registry, instance maps and data collector presented here. As described in the previous subsection, the harmonised BIO-SUSHY (meta)data schema is not completely defined yet, since data requirements from safety and sustainability assessment will be refined alongside the progress in the use cases. This is not only related to additional data needs but also to metadata completeness to fully document the production and testing for reuse by other partners and finally open sharing. This additional (meta)data could be directly added to the Registry entries and the linked data files. However, the improvement would then apply only to these entries, while data providers would still generate incomplete (meta)data for new coatings, which would then need to be amended later. Instead, updating the partner-specific files to integrate the additional information is improving the data management of the partners, and new data is already complying with the higher quality standards. (Re)running the automatic harmonisation workflow then integrates all data into new versions of the harmonised files of existing Registry entries or the first versions of new coating candidates. In that way, data harmonisation and on-the-fly FAIRification can be implemented and continuously enhanced with only minor modifications in the established experimental workflows at the partner institutions.

8. Conclusions

At this stage in the project, the knowledge management and sharing system is focusing on assisting the planning of the experiments supporting the use cases and organising the complex sample and information flow between partners and work packages required during their execution. This is achieved by the combination of four data management tools, the BIO-SUSHY Registry, the instance map tool, the BIO-SUSHY Google Shared Drive and the data collector, together providing the infrastructure for the customised BIO-SUSHY data lake. The interplay of the tools is shown in Figure 15.

Figure 15: BIO-SUSHY infrastructure for experiment planning, data collection, harmonisation, storing and sharing.

Additionally, the concepts and approaches for harmonisation and FAIRification of all research output are outlined, and steps have been implemented for the high-level data documentation and indexing in the BIO-SUSHY Registry that is based on a system of unique identifiers and a limited amount of metadata describing provenance, accessibility and status of the research outputs. The data providers are given flexibility on the formats used to report the different research outputs and solutions for storing them in order to allow direct sharing within the project without delay caused by manual data transformation. The provided preliminary research outputs are now being analysed to generate further detailed reporting guidelines, create highly structured (meta)data schemas for types of research output, and start harmonisation and further FAIRification. The created automatic workflows guarantee that all (meta)data has to be reported only once (WP2, WP3), but can then be transformed into different data formats requested by the data users (WP3 and WP4) and provided as input for downstream analysis, modelling, safety and sustainability assessment.

9. References

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